

USING MULTIMEDIA ELECTRONIC EDUCATIONAL TOOLS IN TEACHING SUBJECTS AT HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Djamolova S.

Teacher at Karshi branch of TITU

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that filling information resources, creating electronic textbooks and courses can be considered as part of the development concept. The need to prepare multimedia electronic textbooks, training courses and multimedia educational complexes arose in higher education institutions. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the manifestations of information and communication technologies (ICT) are the most common concepts in our everyday life. This development process places demands on us, that is, teachers of educational institutions, to create electronic educational literature, textbooks, manuals and other multimedia educational courses on the specialized subjects they have mastered.*

Keywords: *ICT, informatization, LMS, Text, Audio, Animation, Interactivity, Video, Picture.*

Definitely, the capabilities of modern information and communication technologies represent a very broad system, including, in addition to well-known concepts such as computers, multimedia, computer networks, internet, as well as a number of new concepts. Examples of such concepts are information systems, information system management, information system transmission systems, information resource management, data storage. The implementation of electronic education in the sphere of education at the “21st century – the century of informatization”, in each educational institution requires information about the environment of the educational institution in:

- the process of teaching and learning
- the management of the educational institution
- divisions of the educational institution.

What is more important, learning management systems (LMS) are used to organize the educational process remotely or electronically. LMS systems include the main functions of organizing e-learning. Such functions include registering students (teachers, educators creating courses, and persons performing other functions), excluding users from educational courses, creating an environment for independent student learning, mutual interaction between students and teachers individually or in groups and their management, organizing midterm, current and final control, monitoring the level of knowledge of students, exporting/importing electronic educational resources, organizing electronic information resources (electronic libraries). The LMS system, which includes several systems, is the main system for creating, filling and using the electronic information resource system.

Additionally, multimedia presentation is currently the only and most modern form of information delivery. It can be text information, pictures, slide shows, voice-over text, video clips and animation, three-dimensional graphic software. The main difference between presentations and other forms of information delivery is their content enrichment and interactivity, the tendency

to change in a given form and express a reaction to the user's activity. In addition, a presentation can become a key to your website. That is, having access to the Internet, you can view the presentation and get the latest information from the company's website with just one click of the mouse.

Text, Audio, Animation, Interactivity, Video, Picture

Moreover, multimedia technology (multi-set, media environment) allows using several ways of presenting information at the same time: text, graphics, animation, video and sound.

The most important feature of multimedia technologies is their ability to influence the user when working in an interactive information environment.

However, the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process is one of the important moments of informatization of education. Currently, multimedia technologies are one of the fastest growing and most promising areas of information technology.

Multimedia is a set of hardware and software that allows the user to work with heterogeneous information organized in a single information environment. Computer technologies have become an integral part of the lives of many students today. Technical means allow you to bring the ability to work with different types of information, such as sound, text, photos and video images, into educational activities.

The algorithm for creating a multimedia tool for teaching English is as follows:

Let's get acquainted with the program with its interface:

1.1 Autorun launch process

1.2 Opening a new window in startup

1.3 Sorting templates for startup

1.4 Adding background to selected template

1.5 AutoPlay background coloring

1.6 Adding an image to a template from a file

1.8 Adding an image to a template from a file

1.9 Adding a button to the working window

1.17 Connecting the prepared pages together

1.18 Connecting the prepared pages sequentially

It is known that the introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process is one of the important aspects of the informatization of education. At present time multimedia technologies are one of the most rapidly developing and promising areas of information technology. Multimedia is a set of hardware and software that allows the user to work with heterogeneous information organized in a single information environment. Computer technologies have become an integral part of the lives of many students today.

Since the effectiveness of multimedia resources can be influenced by each of the factors mentioned in Hede's model, Layo's findings show how important the overall pedagogical design is. It should be noted that multimedia resources can have a very positive impact on the educational process, but the development of these resources should be approached with caution. Let's ask ourselves: How do multimedia work in the educational process? An effectively designed learning environment (including multimedia educational environment) includes 4 elements:

1. Display of information.
2. Instructions on where to start and how to proceed.
3. Exercises for comprehension and retention.
4. Evaluation to determine whether to repeat what has been covered or move on to the next stage (step).

It should be suggested that the mentioned elements using electronic learning resources in education, in combination with traditional types of teaching should be used. Although it is possible to create all elements without multimedia, using these elements in multimedia makes them more effective, more important. The purpose of bringing information from Meyer's scientific research is to show how multimedia affects memory and the transfer of information if the following principles are observed. These principles relate to the scientific advances of ideas about the limitations of working memory, the principles of encoding in long-term memory.

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